

Quantification of ionic impurities in process liquor using inductively coupled plasma spectrometer and capillary electrophoresis

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Abstract : Ionic impurities are detrimental to Bayer's process for the production of alumina. These cations such as Ca, Cd, Cu, Cr, Ni, Mg, Pb, Mn, V, P, Ga were determined by ICP-AES and for anion such as chloride, sulphate, oxalate, fluoride, phosphate, carbonate and acetate using capillary electrophoresis. The peak separation of each components were found to be within 2 to 4 min. Anion standards were prepared in four concentration levels of 25, 50, 75, 100 ppm and peaks were identified after spiking individually. In the regression analysis, a high correlation factor (R^2) of greater than 0.997 was obtained. The repeatability, reproducibility, and recoveries for the determination of these acids in Bayer liquors were estimated. Cationic impurities were present at very low level (<0.1 gpl) determined using ICP-AES. In this paper, various sample preparation procedure, standard operating condition and its significance for ICP-AES and CE have been studied.

Keywords : ICP, capillary electrophoresis (CE), Bayer's spent liquor, ionic impurities.

Introduction

Alumina (Al_2O_3) is used to extract from bauxite in Bayer process^{1,2}. In this process, the refineries dissolve bauxite in sodium hydroxide to extract the aluminum from it. The soluble part of bauxite in sodium hydroxide solution is referred to as Bayer liquor. The parameter such as temperature, pressure, concentration of caustic of this process depends on the mineral composition of the bauxite. The liquor used in Bayer process for alumina production represents extremely complex matrices. Liquor is very alkaline and it contains very high concentration of soda and alumina. It has also a number of soluble minor impurities which are of high analytical importance and need to be estimated for good quality alumina production. Further, the precipitated aluminum hydroxide form alumina which is used in the aluminum smelting process. Alumina is formed by placing alumina hydrate crystals in a kiln (calciner) and driving off the water, a process referred to as calcinations. Many variables determine the success of calcinations to form alumina, such as size of the $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ crystals. Large crystals are preferred, small crystals are returned to the precipitator. Impurities such inorganic trace elements, anionic organic compounds may

interfere the crystallization process³⁻⁵. Therefore, a quantification of these impurities help to predict the process success of forming large crystals from given Bayer liquor. Capillary Electrophoresis (CE) and inductively coupled plasma spectrometry are the method of choice for determining inorganic as well as other organic impurities⁶⁻¹⁰. These organic carbon compounds have a detrimental effect on the alumina refinery process reducing the productivity of liquor. The soluble impurities in alumina bearing minerals affect the product quality and also disrupt the plant operation. Organics entering the process can also break down and cause volatile organic carbon emissions. The complex liquor's with high ionic strength, metal content and organics make it a challenging sample for analytical chemists¹¹⁻¹³. In the present communication, to address the existing challenges to the analytical chemists a direct method was designed using CE and ICP system with high accuracy and reproducibility for quantification of impurities in Indian Bayer process liquor.

Materials and methods :

Equipments :

Estimation of elemental impurities were conducted on

inductively coupled plasma spectrometer (ICP-AES, Model Iris-Intrepid, XDL), Thermo Electron Corporation, USA. The anionic organic impurities were determined using Capillary Electrophoresis (Model CE-L1, PKS V5.8), USA. The double distilled water was used during all the dilution purpose which was prepared by quartz distillation unit. De-ionized water was prepared by deionizer.

Reagents and chemicals :

Anionic acids standards, 100 ppm (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, F^- , PO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , $\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^{2-}$) and elemental standards, 1000 ppm (Ca, Cd, Cu, Cr, Ni, Mg, Pb, Mn, V, P, Ga) were of high purity (99.99%). These standards were procured from Thermo, UK and Qualigens India Ltd. was used for calibration and method development purpose. All the chemicals, standards and buffers were of analytical and spectral reagent grade. Bayer's liquor samples were prepared in different dilutions with de-ionized water and filtered with less than 0.5 micron (μ) filter.

Sample preparation :

Bayer's liquor :

For elemental analyses, pipette out 5 ml sample liquor into 50 ml volumetric flask containing 25 ml distilled water, shake well and make up to the mark. Took 5 ml of diluted sample into a 100 ml beaker and warm gently for a few minutes, add 5 ml nitric acid and transferred the whole solution into a 50 ml volumetric flask. The solution was cooled and make up to the mark for analysis.

For the quantification of organic impurities such as acids in capillary electrophoresis was prepared by filtering the liquor with micro filter paper. The dilution was carried out using de-ionized water.

Standard preparation :

Multi element mix standard for ICP was prepared using single standard. The matrix was prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of hydrate alumina and caustic for analysis. The mix standard was prepared as per the concentration of analyte in samples. A known volume of each element were taken and mixed together in a 100 ml volumetric flask to prepare a working standard for calibration and standardization.

Anion standards were prepared in four concentration

levels of 25, 50, 75, 100 ppm using 100 ppm stock standards by dilution with de-ionized water. Peaks were identified after spiking individually in capillary electrophoresis.

Results and discussion

ICP elemental analysis :

The quantification of impurities (trace element) using inductively coupled plasma technique was carried out. Characterizations of these impurities were done at different analytical conditions and best condition identified and the same was optimized. The trace elemental data obtained for a typical sample was presented in Table 1. Data indicates the presence of impurities at significant level and need to be estimated for good quality product as well as better process control in the industry. ICP is found to be a very cost effective, sensitive and speedy method of quantification. The method is also a very precise and accurate for the process sample such as Bayer liquor in alumina refineries.

The concentrations of impurities are obtained to be very significant and may go with product alumina which influences the aluminium electrolysis. Some of the impurities such as gallium and vanadium in the liquor are very precious if they could be quantified and recovered. Therefore, estimation of such valuable elements could help in the recovery as by-product from the liquor and help in the process economy.

Capillary electrophoresis (CE) analysis :

A number of trial experiments were conducted on Bayer's liquor for the quantification of various impurities and the best optimized operating condition achieved.

Method development and optimization :

Peak identification :

Peak identification anion standards were prepared in 4 concentration levels of 25, 50, 75 and 100 ppm. Peaks were identified after spiking individually by standards as shown in Fig. 1. All peaks were separated between 2 to 4 min migration time.

Migration time and reproducibility :

The buffer used for this analysis is relatively stable giving reproducible migration time which is shown in

Table 1. Minor impurities concentration in Bayer liquor

Bayer's liquor	Unit	Fe ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	CaO	P ₂ O ₅	V ₂ O ₅	CaO	Cr ₂ O ₃	MnO	Ga ₃ O ₈	MgO
Liq. (1)	(gpl)	0.003	0.825	0.001	0.019	0.35	1.13	0.025	0.001	0.0015	0.05	0.003
Liq. (2)	(gpl)	0.004	0.950	0.001	0.020	0.55	1.65	0.035	0.0015	0.001	0.062	0.002

Fig. 1. Identification of peaks with standards spiking.

Fig. 2. In this study, the migration time standard deviation (percentage) is less than 0.8%, which is presented in Table 2. This makes the calibration curve stable which can be used for longer periods with good confidence and minimal deterioration, hence lesser need for recalibration.

Fig. 2. Reproducibility of migration time.

Components	SD	Mean (Migration time)	%SD
Chloride	0.013	2.48	0.51
Sulphate	0.015	2.66	0.56
Oxalate	0.015	2.77	0.54
Fluoride	0.024	2.97	0.80
Phosphate	0.024	3.10	0.77
Carbonate	0.022	3.36	0.64
Acetate	0.025	3.57	0.70

Calibration-regression analysis :

Correlation factor computed based on four levels of anion standards, 100, 75, 50 and 25 ppm . In the regres-

sion analysis, a high correlation factor (R^2) of greater than 0.997 was obtained for anions such as chloride, sulphate, oxalate, fluoride and acetate. Phosphate has a correlation factor of 0.989 and carbonate has 0.849.

Ions	Chloride	Sulphate	Oxalate	Fluoride	Phosphate	Carbonate	Acetate
R^2	0.997	0.998	0.998	0.999	0.989	0.849	0.997

Bayer liquor analysis :

Two Bayer liquor samples 1 and 2 from the alumina process were analyzed. Since Bayer liquor contains very high concentration of dissolved alumina (80–100 gpl as Al_2O_3) and caustic (160–200 gpl as Na_2O) may hinders the quantitative analysis. It has been noticed that quality of analysis of liquor depends on dilution factor of the samples. For better separation and resolution of peaks the dilution would be higher. In the neat sample carbonate and phosphate were not resolved and are merged into one large peak, therefore known dilution with buffer was carried out. This improves the carbonate peak resolution but the detection of smaller peaks was observed to be less prominent. Therefore, if the analytes are present in the lower concentration, the lower possible dilution is preferred.

Bayer liquor samples are presented in Tables 3 and 4 gives a relatively large peak of carbonate, between 400–2000 ppm. Chloride, sulphate, fluoride were estimated to be between 10–20 ppm. Oxalate, phosphate and acetate were below 10 ppm. Higher value of carbonate in Bayer’s liquor may be due to high absorption capacity of atmo-

Table 3. Data obtained for the Bayer liquor sample-1

Peaks	MT	Area	Area	Height	Height	Amount (ppm) ^a	Component
1	2.53	0.0022	4.1	0.012	1.6	12.22	Chloride
2	2.66	0.0063	11.5	0.086	10.9	12.77	Sulphate
3	2.78	0.0025	4.6	0.058	7.4	11.33	Oxalate
4	2.98	0.0018	3.3	0.077	9.7	9.73	Fluoride
5	3.17	0.0008	1.5	0.027	3.4	5.17	Phosphate
6	3.33	0.0341	2.7	0.412	52.2	441.79	Carbonate
7	3.60	0.0067	12.3	0.116	14.8	34.27	Acetate

^aBayer samples were diluted (200 ×).

Table 4. Data obtained for the Bayer liquor sample-2

Peaks	MT	Area	Area	Height	Height	Amount (ppm) ^a	Component
1	2.46	0.0031	1.7	0.080	3.4	17.24	Chloride
2	2.58	0.0106	5.7	0.424	18.1	21.65	Sulphate
3	2.76	0.0024	1.3	0.062	2.7	11.03	Oxalate
4	2.93	0.0045	2.5	0.172	7.4	24.80	Fluoride
5	2.98	0.0008	0.4	0.008	0.4	5.14	Phosphate
6	3.19	0.1612	86.9	1.527	65.3	2089.21	Carbonate
7	3.56	0.0027	1.5	0.063	2.7	13.99	Acetate

^aBayer sample was diluted (200 ×).

spheric carbon dioxide by caustic shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Carbonates may be also being formed during digestion and precipitation process as the raw material contains a significant amount of organic matter (humus) in some of the Indian deposits. Other impurities except carbonates come from raw material such as bauxite. The mineralogy also plays an important role in dissolution of impurity during alumina process in the refinery.

Higher concentration of these anionic impurities in-

fluences the process parameter which leads to the poor product quality. The value of different impurities obtained in sample 1 is less compared sample 2 may be due to origin of parent minerals as they collected from two different alumina refineries.

The final analytical results of anionic impurities quantified in the Bayer liquor were calculated based on sample dilutions, presented in Table 5. The values obtained are very acceptable and comparable with the value reported

Fig. 3. Electropherogram of Bayer's liquor sample no. 1.

Fig. 4. Electropherogram of Bayer's liquor sample no. 2.

Table 5. Anionic impurities in Bayer's liquor samples (ppm)

Sl. no.	Chloride	Sulphate	Oxalate	Fluoride	Phosphate	Carbonates	Acetate
Sample-1	2444	2554	2266	1946	1034	88358	6854
Sample-2	3448	4330	2206	4960	1028	417842	2798

in the literature. This method of analysis was carried out for the first time in India for Bayer's liquor.

Conclusion

Both ICP (Inductively coupled plasma spectroscopy) and CE (Capillary Electrophoresis) methods have demonstrated an excellent capability of rapid quantification for Bayer's liquor of alumina refinery.

The results clearly indicate that these techniques have been cost effective, rapid and accurate with excellent reproducibility.

Methods utilized are very useful for Bayer's liquor characterization as both are utilized in rapid and simultaneous determination of trace impurities.

Developed methods could be used for quantification of impurities below 1 ppm.

New methodology of quantification would help as an alternative method for analytical chemists for characterization of impurity in Bayer liquor in process and help in process control.

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